

What are the ethical challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia? A Meta-Ethnographic Review

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

What are the ethical challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia? A Meta-Ethnographic Review

Original language title

What are the ethical challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia? A Meta-Ethnographic Review

Review objectives

The main review question is:

What are the ethical challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia?

This main review questions is composed of the following two research questions:

- What are the ethical challenges of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia?
- What are the main ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms surrounding ethical topics in person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia?

Keywords

Advanced dementia, End-of-life care, Ethics, Meta-ethnographic review, Palliative care, Person-centred care, Systematic review

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Searches

Searches will be conducted in the following databases: MEDLINE, Web of Science, Scopus, and CINAHL Complete and PsycINFO by EBSCO Discovery Service.

Preliminary searches were conducted in June 2024 and updated in September 2024. Final searches will be run in November/December 2024 and before the final analysis.

Studies in the following languages will be included: English, Portuguese, Spanish, French and German. There will be no restrictions on the year of publication.

Study design

Inclusion: All types of qualitative studies focusing on ethical challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia will be included. In case of mixed-methods studies, only articles providing quotations from their qualitative component will be included.

Exclusion: Other study designs, reviews, case reports, case series, methodological papers, editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces, grey literature, and theoretical or philosophical articles merely focused on ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms surrounding ethical topics in person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia will be excluded.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Condition or domain being studied

An 'ethical challenge' can be defined as the situation of being faced with the need to make an ethical decision that requires greater rational, emotional or procedural effort in order to be done successfully and therefore tests a person's and/or a healthcare team's ability to make a decision (Martins Pereira et al., 2024). Healthcare professionals providing care to persons with advanced dementia (PwAD) experience various ethical challenges in their clinical practice.

Advanced dementia is a severe stage of dementia that causes significant cognitive and functional decline, memory loss, language impairment, and difficulty performing daily activities (Mitchel et al., 2009). PwAD are a highly vulnerable group. Due to their increased vulnerability, PwAD might often be neglected in their rights to high-quality care, including palliative care. Increased vulnerability is also associated to the development of ethical challenges.

Access to high quality person-centred care for PwAD is often limited and challenging due to uncertainty, increasing ethical doubts. Literature on this topic is either theoretical and philosophical, or focused on one specific ethical issue, rather than on the wide breadth of ethical issues, challenges and implications rooted in ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms surrounding these ethical topics in person-centered care for PwAD.

Population

Inclusion: Adults with advanced dementia, defined as severe stage of dementia that causes significant cognitive and functional decline, memory loss, language impairment, and difficulty performing daily activities.

Exclusion: Persons with other types of cognitive or mental disorders and/or cognitive impairment due to other diseases; persons with early and/or mild dementia.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Inclusion: Qualitative studies focused on ethical challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia. Only empirical studies will be considered. In case of mixed-methods studies, only articles providing quotations from their qualitative component will be included.

Exclusion: Other study designs, reviews, case reports, case series, methodological papers, editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces, grey literature, and theoretical or philosophical articles merely focused on ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms surrounding ethical topics in person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia will be excluded.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Not applicable.

Context

Inclusion: Any context of healthcare provision for persons with advanced dementia will be included.

Exclusion: No context of healthcare provision will be excluded as long as it provides care to persons with advanced dementia.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

This review will reveal the ethical challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia. First, we will identify the main ethical challenges of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia. Second, we will explore the main ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms surrounding ethical topics in person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia, identifying their ethical implications.

Measures of effect

Not applicable.

Additional outcomes

Not applicable.

Measures of effect

Not applicable.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction (selection and coding)

The articles retrieved from of the literature searches will be imported into EndNote and any duplicates will be removed. Data will be independently extracted by one reviewer (S.N.) in an iterative and dynamic process with the other two reviewers (S.M.P. and P.H.M.). Titles, headings, keywords, and abstracts will be screened for a multiple combination of MeSH, CINAHL headings, and free terms associated with “ethical challenges”, “advanced dementia”, “person-centred care”, and “arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms”. Any

disagreements will be resolved by a consensus discussion among the three reviewing authors. The references of included studies as well of any seminal reviews about any of these topics will be screened for potential additional publications.

Data sheets will be used to extract data from the studies. Data will be extracted into a structured data form that will be purposely built for this study. This form will be based on and adapted from PICOS's (Methley et al., 2014; Eriksen and Frandsen, 2018): P = Population (persons with advanced dementia, as per definition above), I = Intervention/exposure/phenomenon of Interest (ethical challenges in person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia, including ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms), C = Context/Comparison (any context of care provision for persons with advanced dementia), O = Outcomes (ethical challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia; and ethical arguments, reasons, principles, values, and norms surrounding ethical topics in person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia), S = Study Design (qualitative studies only; in case of mixed-methods designs, only articles reporting quotations from the qualitative component). Descriptive data will include authors, year of publication, country where the study was developed, year of the study, design, and number of participants in the study. Quotations from original studies will also be retrieved and extracted to the data sheet.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

It is recognized that "qualitative" is an umbrella term that encompasses a diverse range of qualitative research methods and designs, making it challenging to define a 'one size fits all' approach to assessing quality and minimizing the risk of bias. In this meta-ethnographic review, we will follow the Cochrane Qualitative and Implementation Methods Group (hereon Cochrane) guidance on methods for assessing methodological strengths and limitations of qualitative research. Therefore, the Critical Appraisal Skill Programme (CASP) tool specific to the assessment of qualitative research will be used. This tool is endorsed by Cochrane and commonly used for quality appraisal in health-specific qualitative evidence synthesis. All the articles included in our analysis will be appraised and evaluated taking the 10 CASP criteria into account.

To minimize bias, two researchers (S.N. and S.M.P.) will screen the first 25% of retrieved articles independently. Articles will initially be screened by titles and abstract, followed by full-text reading of selected articles. Doubts will be discussed until reaching consensus with the third reviewer (P.H.M.).

Selected articles will be read full by two researchers independently (S.N. and S.M.P.) to identify eligible studies; any doubts will be discussed until reaching consensus among the three researchers.

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

We will develop a meta-ethnographic review, which is a type of qualitative synthesis that offers a greater description of methods and provides a higher order of interpretation when compared to conventional narrative literature reviews. Meta-ethnography is an inductive, interpretative approach based on interpretative qualitative synthesis methods. It is the most utilized qualitative synthesis approach in healthcare research and is particularly suited to developing conceptual models and theories, which is particularly relevant when studying and exploring ethical

challenges and implications. The seven phases of Noblit and Hare's framework for the development of a meta-ethnographic review will be followed and operationalized. Three different methods of synthesis are commonly used in meta-ethnographic analysis. We will use the 'translation' of concepts from individual studies into one another, developing overarching and converging concepts in a process coined as reciprocal translational analysis. In this process, themes from each study at the participant level (first order themes based on quotations from original studies) and at the author level (second order themes based on the interpretative and iterative process among all the authors of this meta-ethnographic review) will be extracted and integrated with themes from the other studies. Further, we will employ refutational synthesis (i.e., where concepts from one study contradicts the concepts from another study) as a means of exploring and explaining tensions between individual studies. New interpretations will be developed as third order themes. Finally, we will build a picture of the whole (a meta-theming or meta-synthesis), using a thorough Line-of-argument (LOA) synthesis, which brings together the ethical, social, cultural and organisational contexts to tell a single story. In this 'story', we will conceptualise an approach to understanding the ethical challenges and implication of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia. This process will be performed in an iterative and dynamic process among the three reviewers (S.N., S.M.P., and P.H.M.). All authors will work together to produce a comprehensive set of synthesized findings.

This meta-ethnographic review will be reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA). To optimize the reporting quality, we will also use the meta-ethnography reporting guide (eMERGe).

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

Not applicable.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

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Review affiliation

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TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Review timeline

Start date: 01 October 2024. End date: 30 September 2025

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

30 September 2024

Date of registration in PROSPERO

11 October 2024

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Publication of review results

The intention is to publish the review once completed. The review will be published in English

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work		
Formal searching/study identification		
Screening search results against inclusion criteria		
Data extraction or receipt of IP		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Preliminary searches were conducted in the preparation of this protocol.

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This review is being conducted as part of an international EU-funded project. Other collaborators might be added, depending on their contribution to the review.

PROSPERO version history

- Version 1.1 published on 11 Oct 2024
- Version 1.0 published on 11 Oct 2024

Review conflict of interest

None known

Country

Portugal

Other registration details

Not applicable.

Medical Subject Headings

Anthropology, Cultural; Dementia; Humans; Patient-Centered Care

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors

Not applicable.

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